

MODELS OF ANODIC DIFFUSION WHEN JOINING PSZ TO NICKEL

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SUMMARY: The anodic process during current enhancement joining of partially stabilised zirconia to nickel was modelled. The model indicated that the current functioned to dissociate ZrO_2 and to promote interphase formation. NiO formation at the anodic junction was categorised into three stages related to the current density applied, oxygen diffusion, reaction control and mixed control by both the reaction and nickel diffusion. In the first stage, no interphase formed but oxygen diffused into the Ni anode; in the second, the thickness of the NiO was proportional to the current density; whereas, in the mixed control stage, the NiO thickness was restricted by an upper limit. The NiO thicknesses predicted by the models agreed with those observed by SEM. The model also provided useful guidance for process control.

KEYWORDS: Current enhancement joining, Interface modelling, Interface diffusion, Interface reaction, Ceramic/metal joining, Joining mechanism

INTRODUCTION

Composites of dissimilar materials rely on good interfacial bonding between the constituents. The general approach is to set up a reaction circumstance by elevating the temperature or making active additions to the junction. Pomerantz proposed a method which introduced electrical current to enhance the bond of glass and metal [1]. Subsequently this method was used to join zirconia and nickel [2]. The basis of the ZrO_2 and nickel joint is shown in Fig 1. The ZrO_2 and nickel to be joined were assembled as a symmetrical electrolyte cell ($Ni|ZrO_2|Ni$) with an extra piece of nickel as the second electrode. The two electrodes were connected to an external DC power supply and a current was passed through the cell from the left side to the right. The left-hand electrode is an anode and the right-hand is a cathode, with respective to junctions I and II. In practice, this cell was heated up to 1241 K, maintained at this temperature for 30 minutes before the external potential was applied. The current ran for 60 minutes and then it was switched off, whilst, the cell was cooled. A strong joint was found at the cathodic junction, which had about 3.5 times higher strength than only diffusion bonding of the same materials [3]. In contrast, no bonding was normally found at the anode if the current density was applied higher than 20 mA/cm^2 . By SEM inspection, a single layer of NiO was found at the anodic junction; whilst, a complex multi-layer structure (Zr-Ni intermetallics) was formed at the cathodic junction [2]. The effects produced by the current and how they enhanced the joint strength are of great interest. Basically the joining process can be described as an electrochemical event. Since ZrO_2 is an ionic conductor, oxygen anions (O^{2-}) are the principal charge carriers in the ZrO_2 and the zirconium cations (Zr^{4+}),

electrons (e^-) and charged holes (H^+) take secondary roles. When the cell is subjected to external potential, charges carried by electrons pour into the junction II where they can exchange their carriers from electrons to oxygen anions in order to enter the ZrO_2 . At the junction I, they swap back to flow away. Electrode reactions occur at both the cathodic and anodic junctions to sustain steady current flow. They are:

Eqn. 1 represents the ZrO_2 dissociated to arrest electrons and to generate O^{2-} ions. (2) is the opposite process. Since the anodic reaction is relatively simple, it could be simulated accurately. The present study is focused on modelling the process at the anodic junction. Specifically, it addresses the dependence of interlayer formation on the process parameters and material constants. This is thought to be a key element in the joining mechanism. In fact, the modelling not only determined the interaction at this junction, but also demonstrated the basic routine for cathodic junction study. Furthermore, the results provided useful advice for control of the joining process.

Fig. 1: Schematic of Electrolyte Cell

STATIC REACTION MODEL

Current enhancement can primarily be understood by first examining its static structure, the so called static reaction model. Suppose that electrochemical reaction is the sole process in the cell, then the relationship between the interphase formation and process parameters could be established by Faraday's law [4]. The law states that the amount of chemical change occurring at an electrode is proportional to the quantity of electricity passing through the cell. For the specific case of Eqn. 2, the law was expressed as:

$$\Delta N_{mole}^O = \frac{t_{O^{2-}} Q}{n F} \quad (mole) \quad (3)$$

where ΔN_{mole}^O is the amount of oxygen anions; n is the number of charges involved per molecule and F is Faraday's constant; Q is the amount of passed electricity and, because only

O^{2-} ions appears in the reaction (2), its transport number ($t_{O^{2-}}$) must be involved. Since current (I) is a derivative of Q with respect to the process time (t), $I = \frac{dQ}{dt}$, a more usefully alternative representation can be derived as:

$$\frac{d N_{mole}^O}{d t} = \frac{t_{O^{2-}} I}{n F} \quad (mole / sec) \quad (4)$$

This directly represents the dependence of oxygen production on the current applied.

In the junction I, supposing that the cross sectional area was stipulated as A_I and there was a NiO layer formed with a thickness $d X_I^{NiO}$, the molar amount of oxygen anions, required by the NiO formation, is represented as:

$$\Delta N_{mole}^O = C_O^{NiO} A_I d X_I^{NiO} \quad (mole) \quad (5)$$

where C_O^{NiO} expresses the mean volume concentration of oxygen in NiO. So then, the changing rate of the NiO thickness is derived as:

$$\frac{d X_I^{NiO}}{d t} = \frac{1}{A_I C_O^{NiO}} \frac{d N_{mole}^O}{d t} \quad (6)$$

Substituting (4) into (6), we obtain the relationship between the NiO thickness and process parameters as

$$\frac{d X_I^{NiO}}{d t} = \frac{\left(\frac{t_{O^{2-}}}{n F} \right) \left(\frac{I}{A_I} \right)}{C_O^{NiO}} \quad (7)$$

where $\left(\frac{I}{A_I} \right)$ is the current density, denoted by i_I and an electrochemical coefficient is defined as $h_O = \frac{t_{O^{2-}}}{n F}$. Therefore, (7) can be simplified to:

$$\frac{d X_I^{NiO}}{d t} = \frac{h_O}{C_O^{NiO}} i_I \quad (8)$$

Since i_I was kept constant during the joining process, (8) can be integrated over a time t with the initial condition $t = 0$, $X_I^{NiO} = 0$. The final solution is

$$X_I^{NiO} = \frac{h}{C_O^{NiO}} (i_I \times t) \quad (9)$$

(9) is the final expression for the NiO thickness. It indicates that the NiO thickness is proportional to a multiple of the current density and process time. The ratio depends on material constants and oxygen concentration. The influence of joining temperature on the thickness was embedded in the transfer numbers ($t_{O^{2-}}$).

ANODIC NICKEL DIFFUSION MODEL

The static reaction model has given a fundamental description of the joining process. However, (9) shows the thickness would increase without limit when the current density tended to be large. This is unacceptable. Hence the process couldn't be reaction alone and the model was modified by introducing a diffusion mechanism. An anodic nickel diffusion model was proposed which stated that both reaction and mass diffusion would occur concurrently in the process. The reaction would start and, once it had dissociated an amount of ZrO_2 , the diffusion would begin instantaneously and continue concurrently with the reaction. As the first step of study, the modelling considered only kinetic aspects, that is limited to the isothermal part of the process. The goal was to determine the thickness function for the NiO formation.

Anodic Simplified Nickel-Diffusion Models

Fig 2 represents a basic scheme of kinetic nickel-diffusion, where the left side is the anode and the right is the ZrO_2 . The vertical axis expresses nickel concentration and the horizontal is distance. Nickel is the diffusing species because its diffusivity is far larger than that of oxygen in NiO [5]. The simplest case is to assume the nickel diffuses only in the NiO layer, which is called the anodic simplified nickel-diffusion model.

Fig. 2: Nickel Diffusion Profile at Anodic Junction

In the simplified model, junction X_I^1 was immobile. Nickel atoms in the anode diffused through the NiO layer to junction X_I^2 , where they met and reacted with the oxygen anions to form NiO. The possibility of Ni diffusing into ZrO_2 had been denied. It notes that the NiO layer actually became a part of the anode. After a given time, the Ni concentration profile would be like the bold line shown in Fig 2, where $(C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^1}$ and $(C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2}$ are boundary concentrations determined by the Ni-O phase diagram. If $C_{Ni}^{NiO}(x, t)$ expresses the nickel concentration function in the NiO layer and \tilde{D}_{Ni}^{NiO} is the chemical diffusion coefficient, the nickel flux, toward the junction X_I^2 , can be expressed as:

$$J_{Ni}^{X_I^2} = -A_I \tilde{D}_{Ni}^{NiO} \left(\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{NiO}}{\partial x} \right)_{X_I^2} \quad (\text{mole / sec}) \quad (10)$$

At junction X_I^2 , the amount of nickel, postulated by the NiO formation, is the same as (5) but the boundary concentration should be used. Then:

$$\frac{d N_{Ni}^{NiO}}{dt} = (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2} A_I \frac{d X_I^2}{dt} \quad (11)$$

Suppose that the anodic reaction is faster than the diffusion process, the NiO formation would be controlled by the supply of nickel atoms, or by the Ni diffusing through the NiO. Therefore, at junction X_I^2 the mass conservation can be satisfied by balance between (10) and (11) as:

$$-A_I \tilde{D}_{Ni}^{NiO} \left(\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{NiO}}{\partial x} \right)_{X_I^2} + (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2} A_I \frac{d X_I^2}{dt} = 0 \quad (12)$$

Re-arranging (12) to give the boundary moving velocity, we have

$$\frac{d X_I^2}{dt} = -\frac{1}{(C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2}} \tilde{D}_{Ni}^{NiO} \left(\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{NiO}}{\partial x} \right)_{X_I^2} \quad (13)$$

Since the ordinary derivative of C_{Ni}^{NiO} can be expressed as [6]:

$$\left(\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{NiO}}{\partial x} \right)_{X_I^2} = -\frac{E_0}{\sqrt{t}} \quad (14)$$

where E_0 is a constant independent of the process time. Substituting (14) into (13) with a coefficient m defined as

$$m = \frac{2 E_0 \tilde{D}_{Ni}^{NiO}}{(C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2}}, \quad (15)$$

the boundary moving rate is obtained:

$$\frac{d X_I^2}{dt} = \frac{m dt}{2\sqrt{t}} \quad (16)$$

Integrating (16) over t , with initial condition $t = 0$, $X_I^2 = X_I^1$, we have the thickness function of the NiO layer as:

$$X_I^{NiO} = X_I^2 - X_I^1 = m\sqrt{t} \quad (17)$$

(17) is the final thickness function for the NiO corresponding to the reaction model (9). It implies that the thickness of NiO would be proportional to \sqrt{t} , where the coefficient m is a constant related to the concentration gradient, boundary concentration and diffusivity of nickel in NiO layer. This function differs from (9) since it is independent of the applied current density.

Anodic Full Nickel-Diffusion Model

The simplified nickel diffusion model obviously comes into conflict with the reaction model. The disappearance of the current factor from the function indicates some important event has been omitted. Therefore the simplified model could not be used to explain the whole anodic

process. This culpable negligence may be caused by the model's original specification. A full nickel diffusion model is proposed to reconcile this problem by releasing the restrictions and eventually establishing a comprehensive thickness representation. Major restrictions in the simplified model are (a) the nickel diffuses only in the NiO layer and (b) the electrochemical reaction must be faster than the diffusion at the junction X_I^2 . These problems are designated as two moving boundaries and interaction transition respectively.

Two Moving Boundaries

When the nickel diffusion in the nickel matrix (anode) is taken into account, the predicament becomes nickel diffusing across two junctions (X_I^1 and X_I^2). Starting the discussion with diffusion mass conservation at the X_I^1 , the flux of nickel input from the left is

$$J_{X_I^1}^{in} = -A_I \tilde{D}_{Ni}^{Ni} \left(\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{Ni}}{\partial x} \right)_{X_I^1} \quad (18)$$

where C_{Ni}^{Ni} is the concentration function of Ni in the anode and \tilde{D}_{Ni}^{Ni} is the diffusion coefficient of nickel. At the NiO side of X_I^1 , the flux of nickel output would be

$$J_{X_I^1}^{out} = -A_I \tilde{D}_{Ni}^{NiO} \left(\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{NiO}}{\partial x} \right)_{X_I^1} \quad (19)$$

At the X_I^1 , the nickel accumulation rate, which is the NiO formation, can be expressed as:

$$\left(\frac{d N_{Ni}^{NiO}}{d t} \right)_{X_I^1} = \left[(C_{Ni}^{Ni})_{X_I^1} - (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^1} \right] A_I \frac{d X_I^1}{d t} \quad (20)$$

According to the mass conservation law, the accumulation part would be equal to the difference between the input flux and the output flux. It is expressed as

$$\left[(C_{Ni}^{Ni})_{X_I^1} - (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^1} \right] \frac{d X_I^1}{d t} = \left[\tilde{D}_{Ni}^{NiO} \left(\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{NiO}}{\partial x} \right)_{X_I^1} - \tilde{D}_{Ni}^{Ni} \left(\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{Ni}}{\partial x} \right)_{X_I^1} \right] \quad (21)$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{d X_I^1}{d t} = \frac{\tilde{D}_{Ni}^{Ni} \left(\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{Ni}}{\partial x} \right)_{X_I^1}}{\left[(C_{Ni}^{Ni})_{X_I^1} - (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^1} \right]} \left[\frac{\tilde{D}_{Ni}^{NiO} \left(\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{NiO}}{\partial x} \right)_{X_I^1}}{\tilde{D}_{Ni}^{Ni} \left(\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{Ni}}{\partial x} \right)_{X_I^1}} - 1 \right] \quad (22)$$

It is found that the sign of the X_I^1 velocity would vary depending on the ratio of the nickel output flux over the nickel input flux.

Assuming $J_{X_I^1}^{in} \gg J_{X_I^1}^{out}$, which means the self diffusion of nickel is larger than substitutional diffusion, we simplified (22) to:

$$\frac{d X_I^1}{d t} = \frac{-\tilde{D}_{Ni}^{Ni} \left(\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{Ni}}{\partial x} \right)_{X_I^1}}{\left[(C_{Ni}^{Ni})_{X_I^1} - (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^1} \right]} \quad (23)$$

Following the principle of (14), the concentration gradient is expressed as:

$$\left(\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{Ni}}{\partial x} \right)_{X_I^1} = -\frac{B_0}{\sqrt{t}} \quad (24)$$

with a coefficient:

$$k = \frac{2 B_0 \tilde{D}_{Ni}^{Ni}}{\left[(C_{Ni}^{Ni})_{X_I^1} - (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^1} \right]} \quad (25)$$

Then the boundary moving rate is:

$$\frac{d X_I^1}{d t} = \frac{k}{2 \sqrt{t}} \quad (26)$$

At the junction X_I^2 , the moving rate of the junction would be the same as (16) deduced by the simplified model. The total thickness increase rate of the NiO layer would be the difference between the moving rates of its two boundaries.

$$\frac{d X_I^{NiO}}{d t} = \frac{d X_I^2}{d t} - \frac{d X_I^1}{d t} = \frac{m}{2 \sqrt{t}} - \frac{k}{2 \sqrt{t}} \quad (27)$$

Integrating the X_I over a time t , the thickness of the NiO layer is obtained:

$$X_I^{NiO} = (m - k) \sqrt{t} \quad (28)$$

where m and k are constants at the given temperature. Eventually the thickness predicted by the two moving boundaries will still be independent of the current density and just smaller than that predicted by the simplified model.

Interaction Transition

Now considering the problem of interaction transition. The mathematical representation that the reaction is quicker than the diffusion of nickel is $\frac{d N_{mole}^O}{d t} > \frac{d N_{Ni}^{NiO}}{d t}$. Substituting (4), (11) and (16) sequentially into this equation, the limiting condition for the simplified model is obtained:

$$i_I \geq (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2} \frac{m}{2 h_O \sqrt{t}} \quad (29)$$

This means the model can only be used in cases of a large current density.

In the reverse case, when nickel diffusion is faster than the electrochemical reaction,

$$i_I < (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2} \frac{m}{2 h_O \sqrt{t}} \quad (30)$$

the motion of boundary X_I^2 would be governed by the reaction. It means that mass conservation at X_I^2 would be satisfied between (4) and (11). The result would be similar to (8) but the boundary concentration should be used. However, the X_I^1 moving rate, given by (26), is not changed. Hence the thickness growing rate of NiO is:

$$\frac{d X_I^{NiO}}{d t} = \frac{h_o}{\left(C_{Ni}^{NiO}\right)_{X_I^2}} i_I - \frac{k}{2\sqrt{t}} \quad (31)$$

and the thickness function is derived as

$$X_I^{NiO} = \frac{h_o}{\left(C_{Ni}^{NiO}\right)_{X_I^2}} (i_I \times t) - k\sqrt{t} \quad (32)$$

Note that $X_I^{NiO} < 0$ would be physical meaningless. Consequently, (32) must have a minimum current density at $X_I^{NiO} = 0$. It is:

$$i_I^{\min} = \left(C_{Ni}^{NiO}\right)_{X_I^2} \frac{k}{h_o \sqrt{t}} \quad (33)$$

It implies that no NiO layer forms when the current density is less than i_I^{\min} . The physical scenario is that the oxygen produced by ZrO_2 dissociation is not enough to form NiO, but diffuses into the nickel matrix.

Hence it is seen that the whole anodic process could be divided into three stages by two critical current densities:

$$X_I^{NiO} = 0 \quad \left(i_I \leq \left(C_{Ni}^{NiO}\right)_{X_I^2} \frac{k}{h_o \sqrt{t}} \right) \text{ oxygen diffusing; } (34)$$

$$X_I^{NiO} = \frac{h_o}{\left(C_{Ni}^{NiO}\right)_{X_I^2}} (i_I \times t) - k\sqrt{t} \quad \left(\left(C_{Ni}^{NiO}\right)_{X_I^2} \frac{k}{h_o \sqrt{t}} < i_I < \left(C_{Ni}^{NiO}\right)_{X_I^2} \frac{m}{2h_o \sqrt{t}} \right) \text{ reaction control; } (35)$$

$$X_I^{NiO} = m\sqrt{t} - k\sqrt{t} \quad \left(i_I > \left(C_{Ni}^{NiO}\right)_{X_I^2} \frac{m}{2h_o \sqrt{t}} \right) \text{ diffusion control; } (36)$$

Eqn. 34 and 35, at the limiting case when $i_I = i_I^{\min}$, produce the same result $X_I^{NiO} = 0$, demonstrating continuity. However, the similar comparison for Eqn. 35 and 36, when $i_I = i_I^{up} = \left(C_{Ni}^{NiO}\right)_{X_I^2} \frac{m}{2h_o \sqrt{t}}$, i.e. the upper limit for (35), does not yield the same result. When i_I^{up} is substituted into (35), it becomes

$$X_I^{NiO} = \frac{m}{2} \sqrt{t} - k\sqrt{t} \quad (37)$$

This is smaller than (36) by $\frac{m}{2} \sqrt{t}$. Therefore, a transition between complete reaction and diffusion control modes has to be considered and is thought to be a mixed control stage. In this stage the reaction and diffusion controls would work successively in the incompatible time domain. To judge their contribution individually, we define a critical time t_c . In the time range from 0 to t_c , the process is controlled by the reaction; from t_c to t , it is controlled by the diffusion. Based on t as the whole process time, t_c would be the termination of reaction control.

In the mixed control stage the function of the layer's thickness would be expressed as two parts:

$$X_I^{0-t_c} = \frac{h_o}{\left(C_{Ni}^{NiO}\right)_{X_I^2}} i_I t_c - k\sqrt{t_c} \quad \text{reaction control} \quad (38)$$

$$X_I^{t_c-t} = (m-k) \left[\sqrt{t} - \sqrt{t_c} \right] \quad \text{diffusion control} \quad (39)$$

In the sequence of the time, the total thickness of NiO would be a linear sum of these two parts, $X_I^{NiO} = X_I^{0-t_c} + X_I^{t_c-t}$. So then,

$$X_I^{NiO} = \frac{h_o}{(C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2}} i_I t_c + m \left[\sqrt{t} - \sqrt{t_c} \right] - k \sqrt{t} \quad (40)$$

where t_c can be worked out from the applied current density as:

$$\sqrt{t_c} = (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2} \frac{m}{2 h_o i_I} \quad (41)$$

It is quite clear that when $t_c \rightarrow 0$, (40) shrinks back to the diffusion control function (36). While the $t_c \rightarrow t$, the function shrinks to the reaction control function (35). Consequently, (40) does express the transition between the two control modes. Since t_c is not a real identified process parameter, it is better to express the relationship in terms of current density (i_I). Substituting (41) into (40) instead of t_c , we obtain

$$X_I^{NiO} = (m-k) \sqrt{t} - \frac{m^2 (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2}}{4 h_o i_I} \quad \left(i_I \geq (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2} \frac{m}{2 h_o \sqrt{t}} \right) \quad (42)$$

(42) is the thickness function in the transition segment. It can still be a function of process parameters and material constants. It links with (35) at the current density of i_{II}^{up} and with (36) when $i_{II} \rightarrow \infty$. It proposes that complete diffusion control (36) would not happen in a real situation and there is an upper limit of NiO thickness. Summarising the deduction, the thickness of the NiO by the full nickel-diffusion model is represented as a system of the segmental functions, that is a combination of (34), (35) and (42):

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} X_I^{NiO} = 0 \quad \left(i_I \leq (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2} \frac{k}{h_o \sqrt{t}} \right) \\ X_I^{NiO} = \frac{h_o}{(C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2}} (i_I \times t) - k \sqrt{t} \quad \left((C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2} \frac{k}{h_o \sqrt{t}} < i_I < (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2} \frac{m}{2 h_o \sqrt{t}} \right) \\ X_I^{NiO} = (m-k) \sqrt{t} - \frac{m^2 (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2}}{4 h_o i_I} \quad \left(i_I \geq (C_{Ni}^{NiO})_{X_I^2} \frac{m}{2 h_o \sqrt{t}} \right) \end{array} \right. \quad (43)$$

VERIFICATION AND SIGNIFICATION

With diffusion data of $\tilde{D}_O^{Ni} = 7.37 \times 10^{-9}$ [7] and $\tilde{D}_{Ni}^{NiO} = 2.03 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2 / \text{sec}$ [8], phase diagram and transport number of $t_{O^{2-}} = 0.35$, (43) has been numerically solved using Mathematica software. Comparison of the mathematical solution with experimental results is shown in Fig 3, where the solid line shows the predicted thickness of NiO layer by the full nickel diffusion model and the stars are the real thicknesses measured using scanning electron microscopy. The model coincided with the experimental results. Especially, no NiO was found when current density of 0.2 mA/cm^2 was applied and there was a thin NiO layer when the current was 0.95 mA/cm^2 , as compared with the calculated $i_H^{\text{min}} = 0.35 \text{ mA/cm}^2$. The threshold for the mixed control was $i_I^{\text{up}} = 6.8 \text{ mA/cm}^2$.

Fig. 3: Comparison of Prediction and Experiment

Considering anodic joining, a significant application of model is its prediction of the phenomenon of anodic junction separation. In Eqn. (43), when the current is more than the critical density (i_I^{up}), the process goes into the mixed control mode. There is a time segment of diffusion controlled NiO formation, then the reaction proceeds faster than nickel diffusion. In sequence, the oxygen produced by the reaction would be more than requirement by NiO layer formation. It would require another sink to absorb those excessive oxygen anions. The considerable event is oxygen combination reaction:

If we recognise that joining was performed at high temperature, the resultant O_2 in (44) would be in gas form and tend to evaporate from the junction to atmosphere. Consequently the O_2 evaporation could function to reduce the cohesion of the two materials. It is not surprising the anodic junction may be separated on those occasions when the applied current density was too high. Only when the current density is controlled, so that the process remains in the reaction control mode, can the anodic junction realise good bonding. Experiments have been carried out to prove this prediction. Table 1 lists the joined strengths at the anodic junction with shear tests [3]. It clearly illustrates anodic junction separation at between 3 and 15 mA/cm^2 which compares with the theoretical value of 6.8 mA/cm^2

Table 1 Joined Shear Strengths at Anodic Junction

<i>Sample</i>	<i>Temp. (K)</i>	<i>Time (min.)</i>	<i>Current density</i>	<i>Shear strength</i>
01	1241	60	0 mA/cm ²	60.8 MPa
02	1241	60	0.05 mA/cm ²	61.5 MPa
03	1241	60	2 mA/cm ²	46.4 MPa
04	1241	60	3 mA/cm ²	42.1 MPa
05	1241	60	15 mA/cm ²	0 MPa
06	1241	60	20 mA/cm ²	0 MPa

CONCLUSION

(1). Electrical current enhancement is a process combining electrochemical reaction with diffusion. In the process, current functions to dissociate the ZrO₂ and provide oxygen at the anode for nickel oxide formation.

(2). The formation of an anodic interlayer (NiO) is governed by the applied current density, process time and material constants. Anodic full nickel diffusion model is a comprehensive description of the NiO formation. In sequence, two critical current densities divide the formation into three stages, no NiO interlayer, reaction controlled growth of the NiO layer and growth by mixed reaction and diffusion control. In the first stage, no NiO formed but oxygen diffused into anode; in the second stage, the NiO thickness is proportional to current density and in mixed control stage, the thickness reaches an upper limit.

(3). Anodic junction joining is directly dependent on the magnitude of current density. Only when the current was adjusted, to keep the process in reaction control, could bonding occur. Larger current led to junction separation because oxygen gas was formed.

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